

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF BLUESCHIST METACONGLOMERATES ON RHEOLOGY AND METASOMATISM IN THE SUBDUCTION INTERFACE FROM DEPOSITION TO EXHUMATION

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The student's full project summary is currently under embargo at the request of the research team due to plans for peer-reviewed publication. The full write-up will be made available after the manuscript has been published. In the meantime, explore this graphical abstract for a snapshot of the project.

ABSTRACT

Studying subduction zones is essential for understanding the geodynamics of plate tectonics, geochemical cycling, and geologic hazards. High-pressure units exhumed from subduction zones preserve pressure-temperature-time (P-T-t) records that provide critical information about fluids, deformation, and rheology of the subduction interface. Although metaconglomerates are often a significant input in modern subduction zones (e.g., Japan), little work has been done to understand their metamorphic histories or effect on subduction interface rheology due to their limited exposures and poor preservation. Crete Island, Greece, is in the forearc of the Hellenic subduction zone and exposes high-pressure metamorphic rocks that record subduction interface processes and peak metamorphic conditions from the Miocene. Included within the high-pressure rocks in Crete is a metasedimentary sequence. This sequence is composed of three outcrops separated by inferred contacts with a greenschist-facies, clast-supported metaconglomerate situated beneath a sequence of blueschist metasandstones. The structurally highest blueschist unit ranges from fine-grained metasandstone at its base and a matrix-supported conglomerate at the top. We present petrographic, geochemical, and geochronologic analyses to constrain the origin, deformation, and metamorphic history of these rocks.

The blueschist facies metaconglomerate matrix is composed of phengite, epidote, and glaucophane. Glaucophane compositions (collected by electron microprobe) are homogeneous both inside the clasts and in the matrix, suggesting growth during subduction. In the blueschist facies metaconglomerate clasts, quartz exhibits microstructures consistent with deformation accommodated by dislocation creep, and micas (phengite and muscovite) preserve a relict foliation. Detrital zircon U-Pb geochronology shows that these clasts with inherited deformation textures were sourced from Triassic to Proterozoic-aged rocks prior to subduction. The greenschist facies metaconglomerate contains albitized and chloritized clasts that preserve volcanic textures, consistent with the Triassic zircon population associated with volcanism during the opening of Neotethys.

The structurally higher blueschists (metaconglomerates and metasandstones) preserve high-pressure paragenesis, while the underlying metaconglomerates were retrogressed to greenschist-facies during exhumation. In contrast with the matrix-supported blueschist facies samples, the greenschists are clast-supported, matrix-poor,

and hence more permeable. The stronger, less permeable, fine-grained metasandstones may have acted as an impermeable barrier for the blueschists while promoting retrogression of greenschist facies metaconglomerates. This study highlights the importance of studying subduction zone metaconglomerates by showing that clasts preserve relic textures and mineralogy, and provide valuable evidence of their provenance and age, as well as processes during subduction and exhumation (e.g., underplating, fluid flow).

Figure 1: (A) Satellite imagery highlighting the Island of Crete (shaded in pink), and the Hellenic trench, outlined in blue (hanging wall marked by blue triangles). Athens, Greece, and the Peloponnese peninsula are labeled as a georeference—the base map from Google Earth Pro (accessed September 2025). (B) Hellenic subduction zone schematic that highlights (1) where prograde metamorphism occurred (blue star), (2) where decoupling and underplating occur (yellow star), and where extension and exhumation occur (pink star). Figure modified after Poulaki et al. (in prep.). (C) Schematic stratigraphic column of the researched outcrop. Color is indicative of facies (blueschist and greenschist), and textures correspond to grain and clast size within the metaconglomerates. Sample 06a is the structurally lowest outcrop and is a clast-supported greenschist-facies metaconglomerate. There is an inferred contact between 06a and 05a, which consists of a very coarse-grained blueschist-facies metasandstone. Another inferred contact lies above 05a, separating it from 04d and 04a, which represent the bottom and top, respectively, of a matrix-supported, metaconglomerate sequence coursing upwards. (D) Photomicrograph of sample 04a in cross-polarized light, highlighting the static growth of glaucophane within quartz and phyllite clasts, quartz microstructures, and permeability differences in clast types (dashed=permeable; solid=impermeable). Clasts outlined in tan are quartzite; the clasts circled in pink are phyllite. Qtz=quartz; wm=white mica; lcx=leucoxene. (E) Photomicrograph of sample 06a in cross-polarized light, highlighting the clast relationships. The clast circled in yellow is sandstone, the clast circled in pink is phyllite, and the clast circled in grey is albitized volcanic rock (dashed=permeable). This rock is a clast-supported metaconglomerate that was metamorphosed to blueschist and retrogressed through greenschist facies. Qtz=quartz; wm=white mica; ab=albite; chl=chlorite.

